

GEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF A LUNAR DARK MANTLE DEPOSIT NEAR CARPATUS MONS: IMPLICATIONS FOR IN SITU RESOURCES UTILIZATION AND TRAVERSE PLANNING. Javier Eduardo Suárez-Valencia¹, Giacomo Melchiori^{1*}, Francesco Santoro De Vico¹, Imma Roman², Kosei Toyokawa³, Riccardo Pozzobon^{1,2,4}, Matteo Massironi^{1,2}, ¹Center of Studies and Activities for Space “G. Colombo”, University of Padova, Padova, Italy (giacomo.melchiori@phd.unipd.it), ²Department of Geosciences, University of Padova, Padova, Italy, ³Department of Earth and Planetary Science, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan, ⁴Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

Introduction: Dark Mantle Deposits (DMDs) are low-albedo, smooth lunar structures interpreted as products of explosive volcanism and rich in Fe- and Ti-bearing volcanic glass [1]. Their diagnostic spectral features near 1 and 2 μm allow their identification in orbital hyperspectral data, and their composition makes them promising targets for in-situ resource utilization [2]. In addition to their resource potential, DMDs provide key insights into the role of volatiles in lunar magmatism. We investigate a large DMD near Carpatius Mons through geological characterization, resource assessment, and the design of a potential exploration traverse.

Materials and Methods: We analyzed the Dark Mantle Deposit near Carpatius Mons using integrated lunar remote sensing datasets. Geomorphology was mapped from Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Wide Angle Camera and Narrow Angle Camera imagery and in-house produced high-resolution DEMs. Surface composition was investigated using hyperspectral data from the Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M3), from which spectral indices and signatures were derived to constrain mineralogy and glass abundance. To evaluate resource potential, we implemented a multi-criteria decision analysis framework based on weighted linear combination, integrating compositional, maturity, and environmental parameters into quantitative suitability indices for oxygen and volatile extraction. Finally, landing site selection and traverse planning were developed using slope statistics, terrain homogeneity, and scientific priority metrics to identify safe and high-value exploration routes.

Results: Geostratigraphic mapping reveals that the Carpatius Mons Dark Mantle Deposit (DMD) forms a thin mantling unit superposed on multiple mare basalt flows of the Imbrium basin. Spectral analyses confirm a glass-rich composition, with band-center shifts consistent with mixtures of volcanic glass and clinopyroxene, supporting a pyroclastic origin. The DMD overlies a complex volcanic setting including lava plateaus, domes, vents, collapses, and rilles, indicating multiple potential eruptive sources. Crater-count dating suggests that underlying flows span $\sim 3.2\text{--}2.1$ Ga [3], while volcanic structures beneath the DMD are younger (~ 1.9 Ga), constraining pyroclastic emplacement to late mare volcanism and linking the

deposit to localized volcanic activity within the basin.

Multi-criteria resource assessment highlights the Carpatius Mons DMD as a favorable ISRU target. Oxygen extraction potential shows moderate to high scores within the deposit, peaking in the central-eastern sector near volcanic plateaus, collapses, and pitted domes, where thicker pyroclastic accumulations are inferred. Volatile potential is uniformly high across the DMD, reflecting mature regolith and abundant volcanic glass that can retain solar-wind-derived hydrogen and indigenous volatiles. A combined suitability index identifies the central-eastern deposit as the optimal extraction zone.

Topographic analysis based on slope statistics enabled identification of three safe landing ellipses, all characterized by low mean slopes ($<4^\circ$). A weighted multi-criteria ranking of candidate traverses indicates that the route departing from the first ellipse maximizes scientific return, operational safety, and ISRU access, defining the preferred mission architecture for exploration of the deposit.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that the Dark Mantle Deposit near Carpatius Mons in the Imbrium basin represents a glass-rich pyroclastic unit emplaced during late mare volcanism. Geological and spectral evidence indicate multiple volcanic sources and localized eruptive activity. Multi-criteria resource modeling highlights the deposit as a favorable ISRU target, with enhanced oxygen and volatile potential linked to glass abundance. Integrated geological mapping and suitability analysis identify a feasible landing and traverse strategy, supporting the exploration of points of scientific interest and resource-rich zones. The proposed workflow is transferable to other lunar pyroclastic deposits, providing a framework for future science-driven ISRU missions.

References: [1] Gustafson J. O., Bell J. F. III, Gaddis L. R., Hawke B. R., and Giguere T. A. (2012) *JGR Planets*, 117, E12. [2] Besse S., Sunshine J. M., and Gaddis L. R. (2014) *JGR Planets*, 119, 355–372. [3] Stöffler D., Ryder G., Ivanov B. A., Artemieva N. A., Cintala M. J., and Grieve R. A. (2006) *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.*, 60, 519–596.